

colouration with ferric chloride and it is insoluble in water. [Found : C, 55.0 ; H, 4.3. $C_{20}H_{11}O_{13}$ (CH_3CO)₉ requires C, 55.5 ; H, 4.44 per cent].

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CONDENSATION OF 3 : 5-DINITRO-4-CHLORO-BENZALDE- HYDE WITH MALONIC ACID IN THE PRESENCE OF ORGANIC BASES

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3 : 5-Dinitro-4-chlorobenzaldehyde (Mittal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1942, 19, 408) has been condensed with malonic acid using various organic bases and it has been found that the condensation takes place smoothly and the yield is almost quantitative when for one molecule of the aldehyde only one of the acid and 0.15—0.25 mol. of pyridine or a similar base are used, as has been previously observed in other cases (*cf.* Mittal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 47).

The condensations were carried out exactly following the method of Pandya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 824. *et seq.*).

Catalyst.	Amount of catalyst.	Yields	
Pyridine	0.15 mol.	1.09 g.	92.37%
Piperidine	..	1.06	88.98
Quinoline	..	1.00	84.74
Without base	..	0.69	50.00

This cinnamic acid was recrystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 82°. (Found : N, 10.40 ; Cl, 12.85. $C_9H_5O_6N_2Cl$ requires N, 10.27 ; Cl, 13.02 per cent).

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